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Abstract: The commercial control of olive anthracnose is mainly based on the use of copper-based fungicides, although alternatives to reduce the quantity of copper in orchards are required. Here, 45 products, including antifungal compounds (commercial and experimental products), inorganic salts, and natural compounds (organic products and plant extracts), were evaluated against *Colletotrichum godetiae* or *C. nymphaeae* by in vitro sensitivity tests or by bioassays using detached fruit. Moreover, copper oxychloride was evaluated for plants bearing fruit. Systemic fungicides and the protectant folpet were the most effective in inhibiting mycelial growth, while copper sulfate and trifloxystrobin were the most effective in inhibiting conidial germination. Fruit bioassays showed that tebuconazole or trifloxystrobin were the most effective against pathogen infection. Plant extracts were ineffective in controlling the pathogen. For potted plants, treatments with copper oxychloride delayed the onset of fruit rot and branch dieback.

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Dr. Gramaje is a specialist in control of fungal diseases affecting
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February 28, 2016

Dear Editor:

I wish to submit a manuscript for publication in Crop Protection. It is entitled "Evaluation of fungicides and natural compounds to control olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* species" by Juan Moral, Carlos Agustí-Brisach, Gentjian Agalliu, Rodrigues de Oliveira, Mario Pérez-Rodríguez, Luis F. Roca, Joaquín Romero, Antonio Trapero. The manuscript is original and represents a significant advance in the knowledge of the fungicide efficacy against *Colletotrichum* species causing olive anthracnose, a serious disease of olive in Spain and other Mediterranean countries.

Despite being the most important diseases of olive fruit, there are a scarce number of control studies

With this manuscript, we are continuing with the studies about olive diseases that we started 15 years ago. The manuscript has been critically reviewed by two colleagues, including a detailed English revision.

Finally, we suggest four preference reviewers for our manuscript with an huge experience in plant disease control. Conversely, we suggest a non-preference reviewer (Dr. Adaskaveg, email: jim.adaskaveg@ucr.edu) due to small scientific discordances.

Thank you very much.

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1 **Evaluation of fungicides and natural compounds to control olive**

2 **anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* species**

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11
12 **ABSTRACT**

13 The commercial control of olive anthracnose is mainly based on the use of copper-based
14 fungicides, although alternatives to reduce the quantity of copper in orchards are
15 required. Here, 45 products, including antifungal compounds (commercial and
16 experimental products), inorganic salts, and natural compounds (organic products and
17 plant extracts), were evaluated against *Colletotrichum godetiae* or *C. nymphaeae* by *in*
18 *vitro* sensitivity tests or by bioassays using detached fruit. Moreover, copper
19 oxychloride was evaluated for plants bearing fruit. Systemic fungicides and the
20 protectant folpet were the most effective in inhibiting mycelial growth, while copper
21 sulfate and trifloxystrobin were the most effective in inhibiting conidial germination.
22 Fruit bioassays showed that tebuconazole or trifloxystrobin were the most effective
23 against pathogen infection. Plant extracts were ineffective in controlling the pathogen.
24 For potted plants, treatments with copper oxychloride delayed the onset of fruit rot and
25 branch dieback.

26 **Keywords:** Anthracnose, *Colletotrichum* spp., control, *Olea europaea*

27 **Highlights:**

28 -Evaluating 45 products against *Colletotrichum* species, causal agents of olive
29 anthracnose

30 -In *in vitro* assays, systemic fungicides (benomyl, difenoconazole, and flusilazole) and
31 folpet were the most effective in inhibiting the mycelial growth of the pathogen, while
32 phthalimide fungicides (captan and folpet) were the most effective in inhibiting conidial
33 germination.

34 -Tebuconazole and trifloxystrobin were the most effective in protecting the fruit against
35 pathogen infection

36 -The use of plants is needed to evaluate the second syndrome of the disease: branch
37 dieback

38 **Abbreviations:**

39 **BCO:** Biological Control Organisms. **PDA:** Potato Dextrose Agar. **SHAM:**
40 Salicylhydroxamic Acid. **RGI:** Relative Growth Inhibition. **RGeI:** Relative Germination
41 Inhibition. **RApI:** Relative Appressorium Formation Inhibition. **EC₅₀:** Effective
42 Concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) Inhibiting 50%. **CI₉₅:** Confidence Intervals at 95%. **DSI:**
43 Disease Severity Index. **RAUDPC:** Relative Area Under the Disease Progress Curve.
44 **ANOVA:** Analysis of Variance. **HSD:** Honest Significant Difference Test.

45 **1. Introduction**

46 Anthracnose of olive (*Olea europaea* subsp. *europaea* L.) is the most important fruit
47 disease of this crop globally (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2014; Talhinas et al.,
48 2005). Spain is the leading olive-producing country, with 25% of the world acreage and
49 nearly 45% of the global production (Moral et al., 2014).

50 Olive anthracnose is caused by at least 13 *Colletotrichum* species that belong to the
51 complexes *C. acutatum* J.H. Simmonds, *C. gloeosporioides* (Penz.) Penz. & Sacc., and
52 *C. boninense* Moriwaki, Toy. Sato & Tsukib. (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2014).

53 For example, *C. godetiae* Neerg. is dominant in Greece, Italy, Montenegro, and Spain
54 (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2014); *C. nymphaeae* (Pass.) Aa is the prevalent
55 species in Portugal (Talhinhas et al., 2005); and *C. acutatum* is the most common
56 species in Tunisia (Chattaoui et al., 2016).

57 The pathogen mainly infects fruit at maturity, causing rot. Subsequently, the affected
58 fruit mummifies, and most of them fall to the soil (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al.,
59 2009; 2014). The olive oil from infected fruit shows undesirable physicochemical and
60 organoleptic parameters (Leoni et al., 2018; Moral et al., 2014). The affected olive trees
61 show defoliation and the dieback of shoots and branches because of the toxins
62 (aspergillomarasmies) produced by the pathogen in the affected fruit (Cacciola et al.,
63 2012; Moral et al., 2009).

64 Olive anthracnose management has been primarily focused on the reduction of the
65 pathogen infection by using copper-based fungicides during the autumn (Cacciola et al.,
66 2012; Moral et al., 2014). Some of the advantages of copper-based fungicides include i)
67 their high efficiency against several olive pathogens (i.e., *Spilocaea oleagina*,
68 *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, and *Pseudomonas savastanoi*); ii) their reduced
69 cost; iii) their low toxicity for olive trees and long persistence on the trees; iv) the low
70 potential for the appearance of resistant isolates due to the multisite mode of action of
71 the Cu²⁺ ion; and iv) their use is authorized, even after flowering, in both organic and
72 conventional olive farming (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2014; Roca et al., 2007).

73 Unfortunately, long-term use of copper-based fungicides may lead to the accumulation
74 of copper in soils, with potential phytotoxic and adverse environmental effects
75 (reviewed by Komárek et al., 2010). To avoid soil contamination by copper, different
76 types of management strategies could be used, such as i) the use of other commercial
77 fungicides with a higher efficacy against the pathogen (Roca et al., 2007); ii) the use of

78 plant extracts with fungicidal activity (Flors et al., 2004), iii) the use of biological
79 control organisms (BCO), iv) the optimization of the fungicide application methods and
80 times (Moral et al., 2014), v) the selection of copper-based compounds with high
81 efficacy against the pathogen (Roca et al., 2007), and vi) the use of new copper
82 formulations (i.e., micron or submicron particles) that allow an important reduction in
83 the Cu^{2+} applied per ha (Civardi et al., 2015). Even so, the number of studies addressing
84 the strategies to reduce the metallic copper applied per ha per year is very limited
85 (Agosteo et al., 2007; Roca et al., 2007).

86 The evaluation of fungicide efficacy under controlled conditions allowed us to screen
87 several antifungal compounds before field trials. During these evaluations, in general,
88 compounds must be tested by *in vitro* assays against the conidial germination and
89 mycelial growth of the pathogen (Dhingra and Sinclair, 1995). Likewise, the evaluation
90 of fungicides to control plant diseases by using plant tissues (i.e., fruit) or potted plants
91 enables an initial screening (Knight et al., 1997). Because soil contamination by copper
92 is a concerning situation in olive orchards, the final goal of this study was to evaluate
93 both alternatives to copper-based fungicides and different copper compounds (or
94 mixtures) that require a lower quantity of metallic copper to effectively control
95 anthracnose. Thus, the specific objectives of this study were i) to evaluate the *in vitro*
96 efficacy of several compounds against isolates of two *Colletotrichum* species, ii) to
97 determine the fungicide and plant extract efficacies against *C. godetiae* using detached
98 olive fruit, and iii) to evaluate the effect of copper-based fungicides on disease severity
99 using potted olive plants.

100 **2. Materials and Methods**

101 *2.1. Fungal isolates*

102 The *Colletotrichum* isolates Col-09, Col-30, Col-68, and Col-104 (Moral et al., 2007),
103 which were obtained from olive orchards in the Andalusian region, were used in the
104 experiments. Isolates Col-09 and Col-30 show characteristics like those of the original
105 morphospecies *C. acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides*, respectively. Isolates Col-68 and
106 Col-104, in contrast, exhibit morphological and physiological characteristics
107 intermediate between those of both morphospecies (Moral et al., 2007). The four
108 isolates were identified as *C. godetiae* by their internal transcribed spacer 5.8S and β -
109 tubulin regions. This phylogenetic species is the dominant one in central Andalusia
110 (Moral et al., 2014). In addition, the Italian isolate Col-116 (Monte Falco, Perugia
111 region), belonging to the species *C. nymphaeae*, was used in some experiments. This
112 phylogenetic species is widely prevalent (> 80%) in Portugal (Talhinhas et al., 2005).
113 Single-spore isolates were incubated at 21-25°C at room conditions for 7 days. The
114 percentage of germination of each batch of inoculum was evaluated to ensure that the
115 conidia were viable.

116 2.2. Compounds

117 We evaluated a total of 45 compounds classified as antifungal compounds (commercial
118 and experimental products with systemic or protectant activity), inorganic salts, and
119 natural compounds (organic products and plant extracts). Moreover, several
120 experimental compounds and plant extracts were included (Table 1).

121 2.2.1. Plant extracts elaboration

122 Extracts from the leaves of three olive cultivars, one extract from *Inula viscosa* L.
123 leaves, and one extract from lemon fruit peel [*Citrus limon* (L.) Burm. f., cv. Verna]
124 were used throughout the study. The three olive cultivars have different degrees of
125 resistance to anthracnose: ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ is susceptible, ‘Picual’ is resistant, and
126 ‘Frantoio’ is highly resistant to anthracnose (Moral et al., 2017). The leaves were dried

127 for 7 days at room temperature (20-25°C) in the dark. The lemon peel was dried at 65°C
128 due to its high humidity content. Subsequently, the dried material was crushed using a
129 hammer mill (RETSCH®, Sk100, 1.1 kW) until the material was ground to a fine
130 powder. The powdered material was kept at 5°C until its use in the extraction process.
131 Plant extraction was performed by the distillation method using Soxhlet equipment.
132 Each plant extraction was performed using 50 g of powder material and 50 ml of
133 acetone as solvent. The essential oil was concentrated by distillation, filtered through
134 sterile filter paper (Whatman No. 1), and kept in a dark glass recipient at 5°C.

135 *2.3. In vitro evaluation*

136 Four experiments were conducted to evaluate the effect of 16 fungicides and four
137 inorganic salts on the inhibition of mycelial growth and conidial germination of
138 *Colletotrichum* isolates.

139 *2.3.1. Mycelial growth assay*

140 Appropriate volumes of each fungicide were added to potato dextrose agar (PDA, Difco
141 Laboratories, Detroit) at approximately 45°C in amounts needed to achieve the required
142 concentrations, which were calculated according to the active ingredient (fungicides),
143 metallic copper (copper-based fungicides), or calcium salt. Mycelial plugs were
144 transferred to new PDA plates with the compounds under evaluation. When fungicides
145 belonging to the QoI class were evaluated, PDA was amended with salicylhydroxamic
146 acid (SHAM) to block the alternative respiration pathway (Wood and Hollomon, 2003).
147 The dishes were incubated as previously described for 14 days, the diameter of each
148 colony was perpendicularly measured twice, and the growth rate (mm/day) was
149 calculated for each Petri dish. There were three replicated dishes for each combination
150 of isolate and fungicide or salt concentration, and the experiment was conducted twice.
151 Using the described method, we conducted two experiments. *Experiment I.* Four

152 copper-based compounds (copper hydroxide [Kocide® 2000], copper oxychloride
153 [Curenox® 50], cuprous oxide [Cobre Sandoz], and copper calcium sulfate [Caldo
154 Bordelés Vallés]), four protectants (captan [Captazel], maneb [Belpron M 50], zineb
155 [Belpron 80] and folpet [Belpron F50]) and three systemic fungicides (benomyl
156 [Benomilo 50], difenoconazole [Score® 25] and flusilazole [Nustar® 40]) were
157 evaluated according to their effect on the mycelial growth of the *C. godetiae* isolates
158 Col-09 and Col-30. All the fungicides were evaluated at doses ranging from 0 (control)
159 to 500 µg ml⁻¹ (Table 1). *Experiment II.* The effect of four fungicides (copper sulfate
160 [Merk Lab.], kresoxim-methyl [Stroby®], tebuconazole [Folicur® 25] and
161 trifloxystrobin [Flint®]) and four calcium compounds (calcium carbonate, calcium
162 chloride, calcium propionate, and calcium silicate) on the mycelial growth of the
163 *Colletotrichum* species was studied as described above. The copper sulfate and
164 kresoxim-methyl fungicides were studied using both *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae*
165 species (Col-104 and Col-116 isolates, respectively), while the efficacy of the remaining
166 products was only evaluated using the isolate Col-104. The calcium compounds were
167 evaluated at increasing doses from 0 to 1200 µg ml⁻¹, while the fungicides were
168 evaluated at doses ranging from 0 to 1000 µg ml⁻¹, except for tebuconazole [Folicur®
169 25], which was evaluated at doses ranging from 0 to 0.5 µg ml⁻¹ (Table 1).

170 2.3.1. Conidial germination assay

171 A 5-µl drop of conidial suspension (2×10^5 conidia ml⁻¹) was mixed with another 5-µl
172 drop of fungicide solution on a microscope coverslip (20 × 20 mm). The coverslips
173 were then placed in Petri dishes with water agar on their lid and base, which were used
174 as humidity chambers. After 24 h of incubation, the coverslips were removed from the
175 Petri dishes, and the conidial suspension was stained with acid fuchsine in lactophenol
176 to stop the spore germination. The percent spore germination was determined by

177 observing 50 conidia selected at random on each coverslip and counting the non-
178 germinated conidia and germinated conidia with or without appressorium. There were
179 three replicates (Petri dishes) of each combination of isolate-fungicide-concentration,
180 and the experiment was conducted two times. The tested doses of the different active
181 ingredients and/or compounds appear in Table 1. Using this method, we conducted the
182 following experiments. *Experiment III*. Four copper-based fungicides (copper hydroxide
183 [Kocide® 2000], cuprous oxide [Nordox® Super 75], copper oxychloride [Curenox®
184 50] and copper sulfate [Merk Lab.]), two carbamates (maneb [Belpron M 50] and zineb
185 [Belpron 80]), two phthalimides (captan [Captazel] and folpet [Belpron F 50]), two
186 triazoles (difenoconazole [Score® 25] and flusilazole [Nustar® 40]), and benomyl
187 [Benomilo 50] were evaluated against the conidial germination of *C. godetiae* isolate
188 Col-09. The four copper-based fungicides and the two phthalimides were also evaluated
189 against the conidial germination of *C. godetiae* isolate Col-30. The fungicides were
190 evaluated at active ingredient or metallic copper doses ranging from 0 to 500 µg ml⁻¹
191 (Table 1). *Experiment IV*. We studied the effect of copper sulfate [Merk Lab.] and
192 kresoxim-methyl [Stroby®] on the conidia germination of *C. godetiae* isolate Col-104
193 and *C. nymphaeae* isolate Col-116 to identify differences in the sensitivity to both
194 fungicides. The experiment was conducted using increasing doses of the active
195 ingredient (kresoxim-methyl) or metallic copper (copper sulfate) that caused low to high
196 inhibition of conidial germination (Table 1).

197 2.4. Evaluation on fruit

198 Three experiments were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of several compounds
199 in controlling olive fruit infection by *Colletotrichum* species. *Experiment V*. In the first
200 experiment using fruit, three copper-based fungicides (copper oxychloride [Curenox®
201 50], cuprous oxide [Nordox® Super 75], and copper sulfate [Merk]) and four

202 experimental products (from AA1 to AA4, Aragonesas Agro company) were tested
203 against fruit infection using detached ripe (black) fruit of the susceptible cv. Hojiblanca
204 (Moral et al., 2008; 2017). For that, previously washed fruit were immersed in a
205 solution of the compound at different active ingredient doses according to the
206 manufacturer (Table 1). The fruit were then air-dried and sprayed with conidial
207 suspensions (10^5 conidia ml^{-1}) of the *C. godetiae* isolates Col-9 or Col-30. The fruit
208 were then incubated in humidity chambers ($22 \times 16 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$ plastic containers) for one
209 month. In all the experiments, untreated-inoculated and untreated-non-inoculated fruit
210 were used as a control and to quantify the percentage of latent infection in the field,
211 respectively (Moral et al., 2009). A completely randomized design with two replicates
212 (humidity chambers) per treatment and 16 fruit per replicated chamber was used. The
213 experiment was conducted three times.

214 In the following two experiments, we used less conducive conditions for the disease:
215 unripe fruit of the moderately susceptible cv. Arbequina. In *Experiment VI*, reddish-
216 purple fruit from cv. Arbequina were treated with four commercial fungicides (copper
217 oxychloride/propineb [Cuprosan® PRO], tebuconazole [Folicur® 25], trifloxystrobin
218 [Flint®] and propineb [Antracol®]), six plant extracts, propolis (propolis [Trabe
219 company]), and citric acid (anhydrous citric acid [Fagron Iberica company]). Fruit were
220 treated with the different compounds by immersion. Treated fruit were then inoculated
221 with a conidial suspension of *C. godetiae* isolate Col-104 as described above. A
222 completely randomized design with two humidity chambers per treatment and 16 fruit
223 per replicated chamber was used. The experiment was conducted three times. In
224 *Experiment VII*, eleven fungicides (five copper-based, three systemic, and three organic)
225 and five plant extracts were tested against fruit infection using green-yellowish fruit
226 from cv. Arbequina. The treatments, inoculation, and incubation were conducted as

227 described in the previous experiment. A completely randomized design with two
228 replicates (humid chambers) per treatment and 16 fruit per replicated chamber was used.
229 The experiment was conducted three times.

230 2.5. Evaluation on plants

231 Three-year-old olive (cv. Hojiblanca) plants bearing greenish-yellow fruit were acquired
232 from a commercial nursery. The plants were washed, dried, and were sprayed with
233 copper oxychloride (Curenox[®] 50) at 2000 µg ml⁻¹ metallic copper. Finally, the treated
234 plants were inoculated by spraying with a conidial suspension (10⁶ conidia ml⁻¹) of the
235 *C. godetiae* isolate Col-68. The non-inoculated control plants were sprayed with sterile
236 distilled water. After inoculation, the plants were placed in a greenhouse at 25 to 30°C
237 in a completely randomized design and irrigated periodically as needed. Four plants
238 (replicates) were used, and the experiment was repeated twice.

239 2.6. Data analyses

240 Inhibition of mycelial growth, conidial germination and appressorium formation for
241 each combination of isolate-fungicide-concentration was calculated as a percentage with
242 respect to the control treatment according the following formulas: relative growth
243 inhibition (RGI) = $[(D_{control} \times D_{Treatment})/D_{control}] \times 100$, where D = diameter of colony;
244 relative germination inhibition (RGeI) = $[(Ge_{control} \times Ge_{Treatment})/Ge_{control}] \times 100$, where
245 Ge = germination (%); and relative appressorium formation inhibition (RApI) =
246 $[(AP_{control} \times AP_{Treatment})/AP_{control}] \times 100$, where AP = appressorium formation (%). The
247 RGI data (*Experiment I and II*) were regressed against the dose or the \ln -log-transformed
248 dose, and the best fit model was selected according to the significance of the regression,
249 coefficient of determination (R^2), coefficient of determination adjusted for degrees of
250 freedom (Ra^2), and pattern of residuals. In the case of the binary variable conidial
251 germination (*Experiments III-V*), regression analysis was conducted using the probit-

252 transformed RGeI and RApI data over the \log_{10} -transformed compound concentration
253 (Horsfall 1956). Subsequently, the predicted values of the effective concentrations (μg
254 ml^{-1}) inhibiting 50% (EC_{50}) of the mycelium growth, conidial germination, and
255 appressorium formation and their respective 95% confidence intervals (CI_{95}) were
256 obtained from the fitted regressions. Adjusted values that did not overlap at the 95%
257 confidence interval were considered significantly ($P < 0.05$) different (Glantz, 2002).

258 In the experiments using fruit and plants, disease severity was assessed weekly by using
259 a 0-to-6 rating scale, where 0 = no visible symptoms, 1 = visible symptoms affecting
260 less than 25% of the fruit surface, 2 = visible symptoms affecting 25 to 50% of the
261 surface, 3 = visible symptoms affecting 50 to 75% of the surface, 4 = visible symptoms
262 affecting 75 to 100% of the surface, 5 = fruit completely rotted and 6 = mummified
263 fruit. The disease severity index (DSI) was calculated for each replication using the
264 following formula: $DSI = [(\sum n_i \times i) / (N \times 6)] \times 100$, where i represents the severity (0
265 to 6), n_i is the number of fruit with the severity i , and N is the total number of fruit
266 (Moral et al., 2008). The relative area under the disease progress curve (RAUDPC) was
267 calculated by the trapezoidal integration of DI values over time. RAUDPC data were
268 subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). Because the number of repetitions between
269 treatments was the same, the means were compared according to Tukey's HSD (honest
270 significant difference) test at $P = 0.05$. The data were logarithmically transformed, when
271 necessary, to the homogeneity of variances or normality. Data were analyzed using
272 SPSS Software (version 14.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago) and Statistix 10 (version 10;
273 Tallahassee).

274 **3. Results**

275 *3.1. In vitro evaluation*

276 3.1.1. Mycelial growth assay

277 *Experiment I.* Both *C. godetiae* isolates (Col-09 and Col-30) showed similar
278 sensitivities to all evaluated fungicides. The systemic fungicides (benomyl [Benomilo
279 50[®]], difenoconazole [Score 25[®]], and flusilazole [Nustar 40[®]]) and folpet (Belpron F[®])
280 were highly effective in inhibiting the mycelial growth of the pathogen, causing
281 approximately 80% inhibition at the lowest evaluated dose (5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The protectant
282 fungicides captan (Captazel[®]) and maneb (Belpron[®]) showed EC_{50} values between 99
283 and 165 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and formed an intermediate group according to their efficacy. The four
284 copper-based fungicides, together with the protectant fungicide zineb (Belpron 80),
285 were the least effective ($247.2 \leq \text{EC}_{50} \leq 374.4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) in inhibiting the mycelial growth
286 of the pathogen (Fig. 1).

287 *Experiment II.* *Colletotrichum nymphaeae* isolate Col-116 was significantly more
288 sensitive ($\text{EC}_{50} = 83 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) to copper than *C. godetiae* isolate Col-104 ($\text{EC}_{50} = 127 \mu\text{g}$
289 ml^{-1}). Conversely, *C. godetiae* isolate Col-104 ($\text{EC}_{50} = 3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was much more
290 sensitive to kresoxim-methyl (Stroby[®]) than *C. nymphaeae* isolate Col-116 ($\text{EC}_{50} = 264$
291 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). According to the remaining products, which were only evaluated using the
292 species *C. godetiae*, tebuconazole (Folicur[®]) caused a total inhibition at 0.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
293 ($\text{EC}_{50} = 0.2 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), while the fungicide trifloxystrobin (Flint[®]) had a mean EC_{50} value
294 of 331 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Among the calcium compounds, only calcium propionate caused a slight
295 inhibitory effect ($\text{EC}_{50} = 1077 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) on the mycelial growth of the pathogen; thus, it
296 is the only calcium compound that appears in Figure 2. Conversely, calcium chloride
297 and calcium silicate promoted the mycelial growth of the pathogen. For this reason, we
298 calculated the doses of these calcium compounds that increased the mycelial growth by
299 50% with respect to the control; these values were 1673 and 1527 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for calcium
300 chloride and calcium silicate, respectively. Finally, calcium silicate did not affect the
301 mycelium growth of the pathogen.

302 3.1.2. Conidial germination

303 *Experiment III.* Overall, the fungicides belonging to the phthalimide class (captan
304 [Captazel[®]] and folpet [Belpron F[®]]) were the most effective in inhibiting the conidial
305 germination of both *C. godetiae* isolates (Col-09 and Col-30), showing EC₅₀ values ≤
306 2.2 µg ml⁻¹. Cuprous oxide (Cobre Sandoz[®]) had a similar (EC₅₀ values ≤ 2.2 µg ml⁻¹)
307 efficacy as the phthalimide fungicides. Isolate Col-09 was significantly more resistant to
308 copper sulfate than isolate Col-30 (EC₅₀ = 62.6 vs. EC₅₀ = 1.2 µg ml⁻¹). Benomyl
309 (Benomilo 50; EC₅₀ = 223.3 µg ml⁻¹), the triazole fungicides (EC₅₀ ≥ 23.0 µg ml⁻¹), and
310 zineb (Belpron 80) (EC₅₀ = 28.9 µg ml⁻¹) had scarcely any efficacy against the conidial
311 germination of isolate Col-09. Furthermore, copper oxychloride (Curenox[®] 50) and
312 copper sulfate were the most effective fungicides (EC₅₀ ≤ 0.6 µg ml⁻¹) against the
313 appressorium formation of isolate Col-09, while the fungicides captan (Captazel; EC₅₀ =
314 0.68 µg ml⁻¹) and cuprous oxide (Nordox[®] Super 75; EC₅₀ = 1.18 µg ml⁻¹) inhibited the
315 appressorium formation of isolate Col-30 (Table 2). The ability to inhibit conidial
316 germination was not correlated ($r = 0.148$; $P = 0.626$) with the ability to inhibit
317 appressorium formation.

318 *Experiment IV.* In the experiment investigating the effect of copper sulfate and
319 kresoxim-methyl (Stroby[®]) on the spore germination of the two *Colletotrichum* species,
320 the *C. nymphaeae* isolate Col-116 was significantly less sensitive to kresoxim-methyl
321 (Stroby[®]) than the *C. godetiae* isolate Col-104 according to the EC₅₀ values for the
322 conidial germination (EC₅₀ = 107.49 µg ml⁻¹ vs. EC₅₀ = 7.01 µg ml⁻¹, respectively) and
323 appressorium formation (EC₅₀ = 42.56 µg ml⁻¹ vs. EC₅₀ = 4.66 µg ml⁻¹, respectively).
324 Conversely, both isolates Col-116 and Col-104 showed similar ($P > 0.05$) sensitivities
325 to copper sulfate according to the EC₅₀ values of the conidial germination (EC₅₀ = 1.52

326 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ vs. $\text{EC}_{50} = 7.70 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively) and appressorium formation ($\text{EC}_{50} = 1.41$
327 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ vs. $\text{EC}_{50} = 2.53 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively).

328 3.2. Evaluation on fruit

329 *Experiment V.* Because both fungal isolates had a similar virulence ($P = 0.08$) and the
330 interaction isolate-treatment was not significant ($P = 0.9461$), the data were combined.
331 Only the fruit that were treated with the formulation AA2 (copper hydroxide/folpet)
332 showed a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in the severity of symptoms with respect to
333 the untreated control (*data no shown*). In all the experiments, the non-inoculated control
334 fruit did not show any symptoms (i.e., latent infection).

335 *Experiment VI.* The fungicides tebuconazole (Folicur[®] 25) and trifloxystrobin (Flint[®])
336 were the only compounds that caused a significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in the severity
337 of symptoms with respect to the untreated olive fruit. The remaining evaluated
338 compounds were ineffective (Fig. 3).

339 *Experiment VII.* The most effective fungicides in inhibiting the pathogen infection were
340 tebuconazole (Folicur[®]) and trifloxystrobin (Flint[®]), which caused an important
341 reduction (40-fold) in the disease severity (RAUDPC). At the same time, trifloxystrobin
342 (Flint[®]) had a similar ($P > 0.05$) effect as the copper oxychloride/propineb formulation
343 (Cuprosan-PRO). The effect of the last formulation did not significantly differ ($P >$
344 0.05) from that of the cuprous oxide (Nordox[®] Super 75). The remaining compounds
345 failed to control fruit infection, showing no significant ($P > 0.05$) differences with the
346 inoculated control fruit (Fig. 4).

347 3.3. Evaluation on plants

348 The first symptoms on the untreated and inoculated plants were observed seven days
349 after inoculation, while these symptoms were detected 14 days after inoculation in the
350 plants treated with copper oxychloride (Curenox[®] 50). The RAUDPC values calculated

351 at the end of the experiment were 93.6 and 63.2% for the control and treated plants ($P =$
352 0.007), respectively (Fig. 5). The dieback of branches was first detected in the untreated
353 plants, but it was also observed 3-wk later in the copper oxychloride-treated plants.

354 **4. Discussion**

355 Copper fungicides have become indispensable to control plant diseases and are one of
356 the most important components of olive disease control programs. The long-term use of
357 copper fungicides in agriculture negatively impacts beneficial organisms, soil fertility,
358 aquifers, and final consumers (Borkow and Gabbay, 2009). Even so, only a small
359 number of studies have been conducted to reduce or limit the use of copper-based
360 fungicides on olive orchards (Agosteo et al., 2007; Roca et al., 2007).

361 In our study, systemic fungicides (benomyl, difenoconazole, and flusilazole) had the
362 highest efficacy in inhibiting the mycelial growth of the pathogen, whereas the
363 protectant fungicides (captan and folpet) and some copper-based compounds showed an
364 important efficacy in inhibiting the conidial germination. This fact explains the frequent
365 use of copper-based and organic fungicide mixtures to control olive diseases (Cacciola
366 et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2014). Calcium can influence the control of some plant
367 diseases caused by fungi due to its ability to inhibit the activity of some pathogen
368 enzymes and to reinforce the cell wall of plant tissues (Rahman and Punja, 2007). Here,
369 only calcium propionate was able to inhibit the mycelial growth of the pathogen. In
370 field conditions, we observed a certain correlation between the content of calcium in the
371 olive fruit and its resistance to the pathogen; however, further research is needed to
372 elucidate the role of calcium in olive fruit resistance to the pathogen (Moral et al.,
373 2014).

374 The species of *Colletotrichum* can be considered more resistant to metallic copper than
375 other olive pathogens, such as *S. oleagina* (EC_{50} from 1 to 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and *P.*

376 *cladosporioides* (EC50 from 0.1 to 1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Roca et al., 2007). However, we
377 observed important differences between *Colletotrichum* isolates according their
378 sensitivity to copper. These differences could be due to the selection pressure exerted by
379 the repeated application of copper-based fungicides in areas where olive anthracnose is
380 endemic. Nevertheless, studies treating a major group of *Colletotrichum* spp. isolates
381 collected from different olive growing regions across the world with standardized
382 copper treatments would be needed to determine the effect of copper treatments on the
383 resistance of the pathogen to copper.

384 The high efficacy that folpet/copper hydroxide formulation (AA2) showed in protecting
385 ripe olive fruit also agrees with the folpet efficacy in inhibiting mycelial growth and
386 conidial germination. When we used less susceptible fruit (i.e., greenish-yellow fruit of
387 cv. Arbequina), the fungicides trifloxystrobin (Flint[®]) and tebuconazole (Folicur[®]) were
388 the most effective in protecting the fruit against pathogen infection, followed by some
389 of the copper-based fungicides (Cuprosan PRO and Nordox[®] Super 75). The
390 effectiveness of copper-based fungicides in controlling anthracnose has long been
391 known by olive farmers in the Mediterranean basin (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al.,
392 2014). In Europe, the use of copper-based fungicides decreased by 43% during the
393 period from 1993-2003 in favor of other classes of fungicides, such as carbamates,
394 quinolones, and strobilurins (Eurostat, 2007). However, copper-based compounds still
395 are dominant in olive and grapevine orchards in Europe (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et
396 al., 2014).

397 Strobilurin fungicides such as azoxystrobin, pyraclostrobin, kresoxim-methyl, or some
398 formulated mixtures (i.e., Pristine, pyraclostrobin/boscalid) provide good anthracnose
399 control in a variety of fruit crops (Bartlett et al., 2002). In the case of olive anthracnose,
400 Agosteo et al. (2007) detected an elevated efficacy of the fungicide azoxystrobin. In

401 southern Spain, the homemade mixture of copper oxychloride (Cuproflow) and
402 trifloxystrobin (Flint) is highly effective in controlling the disease (J. Moral,
403 unpublished). Strobilurins are mainly protectant fungicides, although this chemical
404 group shows a partial systemic movement on the fruit. For this reason, the mixtures of
405 copper-based and strobilurin fungicides are promising treatments when farmers need a
406 curative effect. Additionally, mixtures of strobilurin and other groups of fungicides,
407 together with rotations with other compounds, are essential to prevent the development
408 strains of the pathogen resistant to these compounds (Bartlett et al., 2002).

409 In our bioassays, tebuconazole was highly effective in controlling *Colletotrichum*
410 infection on fruit, which has been previously described for other triazole (hexaconazole
411 and thiabendazole) compounds (Penninsi et al., 1993). In the laboratory experiments,
412 we observed that tebuconazole also had an eradicated effect on natural latent infections.
413 However, tebuconazole is a fat-soluble fungicide, and its use as a post-flowering
414 treatment in olive trees is prohibited (Moral et al., 2014).

415 In our study, the evaluated natural compounds and plant extracts were ineffective in
416 controlling olive anthracnose. Recently, Pangallo et al. (2017) showed that pomegranate
417 (*Punica granatum*) peel extract is highly effective in treatments of olive fruit inoculated
418 with the *Colletotrichum*. Additionally, the pomegranate extract was more effective than
419 copper under field conditions.

420 Finally, our results using potted olive plants showed that the plants treated with copper
421 oxychloride had a delayed onset of fruit rot and branch dieback. The use of plants is
422 essential when the objective of a study is to quantify the effect of fungicides on branch
423 dieback syndrome.

424 In summary, this current work represents the first evaluation of organic and copper-
425 based fungicides and natural compounds according to their effectiveness in controlling

426 olive anthracnose to reduce the environmental impact of copper. According to this
427 study, the selection of highly effective copper-based compounds or new formulations of
428 these with a low copper concentration and the mixture of copper-based fungicides with
429 fungicides belonging to other chemical groups, such as strobilurins, could help control
430 olive anthracnose and reduce the use of copper in olive orchards.

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506 **Figure captions**

507

508 **Fig. 1.** Effective concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of different compounds (Table 1) inhibiting
509 50% (EC_{50}) of the mycelium growth of the *Colletotrichum godetiae* isolate Col-104 and
510 the *C. nymphaeae* isolate Col-116, causal agents of olive anthracnose. For each
511 fungicide and isolate, the points represent the average of six Petri dishes, and the lines
512 represent the 95% confidential intervals.

513 **Fig. 2.** Effective concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of different compounds (Table 1) inhibiting
514 50% (EC_{50}) of the mycelium growth of the *Colletotrichum godetiae* isolate Col-104 and
515 the *C. nymphaeae* isolate Col-116, causal agents of olive anthracnose. For each
516 fungicide and isolate, the points represent the average of six Petri dishes, and the lines
517 represent the 95% confidential intervals.

518 **Fig. 3.** Effect of four fungicides, six plant extracts, propolis and citric acid (Table 1) on
519 the relative area under the disease progress curve (RAUDPC) in the greenish-yellow
520 olive fruit of the moderately susceptible cv. Arbequina inoculated with *Colletotrichum*
521 *godetiae*. Bars represent the average of 96 fruit. For each fungicide, mean values with
522 the same letter are not significantly different according to Tukey's HSD test at $P = 0.05$.

523 **Fig. 4.** Effect of eleven fungicides and five plant extracts (Table 1) on the relative area
524 under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) in the greenish-yellow olive fruit of the
525 moderately susceptible cv. Arbequina inoculated with *Colletotrichum godetiae*. Bars
526 represent the average of 96 fruit. For each fungicide, mean values with the same letter
527 are not significantly different according to Tukey's HSD test at $P = 0.05$.

528 **Fig. 5.** Disease severity progress on green-yellowish olive fruit in potted olive plants of
529 the cv. Hojiblanca inoculated with the *Colletotrichum godetiae* isolate Col-68. Before
530 inoculation, plants were sprayed with copper oxychloride (Curenox[®] 50) at $2000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
531 of metallic copper or with sterile distilled water (inoculated control). For each
532 treatment, points represent the average of 1200 fruit. Vertical bars are the standard error
533 of the means.

534

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Figure(s)

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Table 1. Antifungal compounds, inorganic salts, and natural compounds evaluate against *Colletotrichum* spp.

Trade name	Company	Active ingredient(s)	Class (FRAC number) ^u	Systemic action	Doses (µg/ml) ^l and Experiment (From I to VII)		
					Mycelial growth	Conidial germination	Inoculated fruit
Cuprofol	Nufarm	Copper calcium sulfate/ Folpet	Inorganic (M1)/ Phthalimide (M4)	No	-	-	1060/ 530 (VII)
Cuprosan PRO®	Bayer CropScience	Copper oxychloride/ Propineb	Inorganic (M1)/ carbamate (DMDC)(M3) ^v	No	-	-	800/ 600 (VI & VII)
Curenox 50®	Ind. Químicas del Vallés	Copper oxychloride	Inorganic (M1)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	1000 (V)
Cal. Bordelés Vallés	Ind. Químicas del Vallés	Copper calcium sulfate	Inorganic (M1)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	-	-
Funguran-OH	Nufarm	Copper hydroxide	Inorganic (M1)	No	-	-	10000 (VII)
Kocide 2000®	Du Pont	Copper hydroxide	Inorganic (M1)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	-
Cobre Sandoz	Sandoz	Cuprous oxide	Inorganic (M1)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	-	-
Nordox Super 75®	Arysta LifeScience	Cuprous oxide	Inorganic (M1)	No	-	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	1000 (V) 2600 (VII)
-	Merk Lab.	Copper sulfate	Inorganic (M1)	No	1;10;100;1000 (II)	0.5;2;8;32 (IV)	1000 (V) 2000 (VII)
-	Panreac AppliChem	Calcium carbonate	Inorganic salt (various)	No	1;10;100;1000;1200 (II)	-	-
-	Panreac AppliChem	Calcium chloride	Inorganic salt (various)	No	1;10;100;1000;1200 (II)	-	-
-	Sigma-Aldrich-Fluka	Calcium propionate	Inorganic salt (various)	No	1;10;100;1000;1200 (II)	-	-
-	Sigma-Aldrich-Fluka	Calcium silicate	Inorganic salt (various)	No	1;10;100;1000;1200 (II)	-	-
AA1^z	Aragonesas Agro	Copper oxychloride/ Maneb/ Zineb	Inorganic (M1)/ Carbamate (EBDC)(M3)/ Carbamate (DMDC) (M3)	No	-	-	180/ 100/ 100 (V)
AA2^z	Aragonesas Agro	Copper hydroxide/ Folpet	Inorganic (M1)/ Phthalimide (M4)	No	-	-	100/ 100 (V)
AA3^z	Aragonesas Agro	Copper oxychloride	Inorganic (M1)	No	-	-	1000 (V)
AA4^z	Aragonesas Agro	Folpet	Phthalimide (M4)	No	-	-	100 (V)
Benomilo 50	Aragonesas Agro	Benomyl	DMI ^w -Benzimidazole (3)	Yes	5;10;25;50;500 (I)	250;500 (III)	-
Score 25®	Syngenta	Difenoconazole	DMI-triazole (3)	Yes	5;10;25;50;500 (I)	250;500 (III)	-
Nustar 40®	Du Pont	Flusilazole	DMI-triazole (3)	Yes	5;10;25;50;500 (I)	250;500 (III)	-
Folicur 25®	Bayer CropScience	Tebuconazole	DMI-triazole (3)	Yes	0.01;0.05;0.1;0.5;1 (II)	-	600 (VI & VII)
Flint®	Bayer CropScience	Trifloxystrobin	QoI ^x (11)	Yes	1;10;100;1000 (II)	-	100 (VI & VII)
Stroby®	Basf	Kresoxim-methyl	QoI (11)	Yes	1;10;100;1000 (II)	0.1;1;10;100 (IV)	200 (VII)
Antracol®	Bayer CropScience	Propineb	Carbamate (DMDC)(M3)	No	-	-	900 (VI)
Belpron M 50	Probelte	Maneb	Carbamate (EBDC)(M3)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	-
Belpron 80	Probelte	Zineb	Carbamate (DMDC)(M3)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	-
Belpron F 50	Probelte	Folpet	Phthalimide (M4)	No	5;10; 25;50;500 (I)	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	-
Captazel	Syngenta	Captan	Phthalimide (M4)	No	50;125;250;500 (I)	0.5;1.5;4.5;13.5 (III)	-
Propolis	Trabe	Propolis	Natural product	No	-	-	30000 (VI)
Anhydrous citric Acid	Fagron ibérica	C ₆ H ₈ O ₇	Oxidizer	No	-	-	50000 (VI)
Bio 150 Cítrico	Agromed	Citrus extract	Plant extract	No	-	-	40000 (VI & VII)
Bio 75 Tomillo	Agromed	<i>Thymus</i> sp. extract	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VII)
Oleathbio tomillo	Trabe	<i>Thymus</i> sp. Extract	Plant extract	No	-	-	30000 (VII)
Belladonna leaves	Fagron ibérica	<i>Atropa belladonna</i>	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VI)

Fluid extract 'Ginkgo biloba'	Fagron ibérica	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Plant extract	No	-		50000 (VI)
Fluid extract 'Ivy leaves'	Fagron ibérica	<i>Hedera helix</i>	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VI)
Fluid extract 'Walnut leaves'	Fagron ibérica	<i>Juglans nigra</i>	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VI)
Fluid extract 'Salvia'	Fagron ibérica	<i>Salvia officinalis</i>	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VI)
Fluid extract 'Elder flower'	Fagron ibérica	<i>Sambucus nigra</i>	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VI)
-	Own elaboration	<i>Inula viscosa</i>	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VII)
-	Own elaboration	<i>Olea europea</i> cv. Lechín de Sevilla	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VII)
-	Own elaboration	<i>Olea europea</i> cv. Frantoio	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VII)
-	Own elaboration	<i>Olea europea</i> cv. Meski	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VII)
-	Own elaboration	<i>Olea europea</i> cv. Picual	Plant extract	No	-	-	50000 (VII)

[†]Doses of active ingredient (commercial and experimental antifungal compounds), metallic Cu (copper-based fungicides), calcium (calcium salts), or plant extract

[‡]Group numbers are assigned by the Fungicide Resistance Action Committee (FRAC) according to different modes of actions (for more information, see <http://www.frac.info/>).

[§]DMDC = dimethyl dithiocarbamate

[¶]DMI = demethylation (sterol) inhibitor

[×]QoI = quinone outside inhibitor (strobilurin)

[‡]EBDC = ethylene bisdithiocarbamate

[‡]Experimental products

Table 2. Effective concentrations (mg l^{-1}) of different fungicides inhibiting 50% of the conidial germination and appressorium development (EC_{50}) of two isolates (Col-09 and Col-30) of *Colletotrichum godetiae* causing olive anthracnose

Class	Active Ingredient	Effective concentration (mg l^{-1}) inhibiting 50% (EC_{50})			
		Conidial germination ^w		Appressorium development ^x	
		Col-09 ^y	Col-30	Col-09	Col-30
Inorganic fungicides	Copper hydroxide	6.61 b ^z	12.64 a	2.25 bc	-
	Copper oxychloride	12.02 b	<0.5	<0.5	4.26 b
	Cuprous oxide	2.22 ab	0.54 a	1.33 b	1.18 a
	Copper sulfate	62.57 c	1.24 a	0.58 a	2.04 b
Carbamate	Maneb	5.25 b	-	1.94 bc	-
	Zineb	28.86 b	-	4.716 c	-
Phthalimide	Captan	0.74 a	0.78 a	2.19 bc	0.68 a
	Folpet	1.37 a	2.14 a	2.12 bc	2.11 b
Benzimidazole	Benomyl	223.36 c	-	-	-
Triazole	Difenoconazole	82.47 c	-	-	-
	Flusilazole	22.97 b	-	-	-

^w EC_{50} of conidial germination was calculated as predicted value of the regression: probit-transformed inhibition over \log_{10} -transformed fungicide concentration.

^x EC_{50} of appressorium develop was calculated as predicted value of the regression: inhibition over \log_{10} -transformed fungicide concentration.

^yFor each column values with the same letter are not significant different according to 95% Confidential Intervals (CI_{95}).

^zValues represent the means of six repetitions (three per experiment).